

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FUNCTION WORDS IN ENGLISH

Jawgasharova Amina Alawaddinovna

PhD student at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

ajawgasharova@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15179325>

Annotation: *This article presents information about theoretical development of function words in English language system and identifies the primary sources on the definition of these function words. It defines the grammatical role of function words according to several authors' theories, definitions and viewpoints.*

Key words: *grammar, function words, content words, the closed class, lexical words, grammatical words.*

Introduction. Grammar is the basic contribution in making sentence. Word classes became the primary principal of grammar. Then, this study investigated function word and lexical word that used in the sentences. [3.4] In English grammar, a function word is a word that expresses a grammatical or structural relationship with other words in a sentence. In contrast to a content word, a function word has little or no meaningful content. Nonetheless, as writer Ammon Shea points out, “the fact that a word does not have a readily identifiable meaning does not mean that it serves no purpose”. [4.1]

In English grammar the words belong to either content or function words. According to dictionaries content or lexical words mean meaning, information while function is necessary words for grammar.

Function and lexical words are the important in English. They have the main point to build a phrase or a sentence. Kennedy. G states that “there is a fundamental distinction between function words (sometimes called “grammatical words” or “structural words”) and content words (sometimes called “lexical words”). There are about 250 function words in English (e.g. and, of, a, in, to, it, is, was, that – these ten words alone make up over 20 percent of all the words we ever use)”. [3.4]

Function words are known as structure words, grammatical words, grammatical functors, grammatical morphemes, function morphemes, form words and empty words. According to social psychologist James Pennebaker, “function words account for less than one-tenth of 1 percent of your vocabulary but make up almost 60 percent of the words you use”. [4.2]

Function words are not only very common, they also have a central part in linking content words together and uttering grammatical meanings. Function words are said to belong to “closed classes”, which do not admit new words. Typical of

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

function words have many senses. The Oxford English Dictionary gives over eight meanings of *when*, 40 meanings of *in* and over 60 meanings of the preposition *of*. [3.6]

Lexical and Functional Grammar defines and separates by category what is content-driven from what is abstract. The lexical categories (or Form Class words) come to include: Nouns, Verbs, Adjectives, and Adverbs (with some discussion of how prepositions might straddle the functional category), while functional categories (or Structure Class words) come to include Determiners, Auxiliary/Modals, Pronouns, Complementizers, and Qualifiers. [2.31]

Function words have been operationally defined, in this study, as words which are not nouns, lexical verbs, adjectives and adverbs of a certain kind. This definition included determiners, pronouns, auxiliary verbs, prepositions, conjunctions, numbers as well as certain types of adverbs. [5.2]

According to Baayen, Piepenbrock and Gulikers function words include pronouns, prepositions, articles, conjunctions, and auxiliary verbs. Whereas the average native English speaker has an impressive vocabulary of well over 100,000 words, fewer than 400 are function words. [6.347] However, there are several opinions about the words which include in function words. The following scientists categorized quite different. According to Teschner and Evan function word has four types such as pronoun, determiner, quantifier, and preposition. But according to Jeffries, it has five categories such as pronoun, determiner, preposition, conjunction, and auxiliary verb. [3.11]

Function words include determiners, conjunctions, prepositions, pronouns, auxiliary verbs, modals, qualifiers, and question words. Content words are words with specific meanings, such as nouns, adjectives, adverbs, and main verbs. Function words belong to the closed class of words in grammar because it is very uncommon to have new function words created in the course of speech. [1.66]

Thus, function words might be pronouns, prepositions, articles, conjunctions and auxiliary verbs. They also known as structure words that assist the form word classes in a sentence. These words belong to the closed class of words in grammar which can give grammatical information about other words in a sentence and cannot be isolated from these words. So that both content and function words have highly essential role on not only making up sentence but also expressing some information.

The most important distinction between content and function words is semantic. Content words have referential meaning in that they refer to entities, actions and qualities of these entities and actions in the outside world (e.g. book, run, good,

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

easily). On the other hand, function words have relational meaning in that they express relations among entities, actions and qualities (e.g. *book of poems, run for your life, too good to be true*). While content words have independent meanings that

could be defined in a dictionary, function words mean little out of the context of a sentence. For instance, the content words *book, poem, run, life, good, true* would invoke concepts even out of context whereas the function words *of, for, too, be, your, to* would fail to do so. As such, according to Aitchison content words are often regarded as the “lexicon proper” while Cook refers function words are considered to belong in the grammar. Thus, separating content words and function words in word lists make as much sense as separating vocabulary and grammar. Function words can then be assessed as part of the grammatical competence or taught as part of a grammatical syllabus. [5.3]

Thus, content words have lexical and specific meaning while structure words have grammatical meaning in relation to other words in a sentence.

In conclusion, function words are the words that do not state exact meaning but they refer to several grammatical rules and relationships among other words within in a sentence.

References:

1. Абдулахатова Ш.А. Functional-pragmatic features of function words in communicative discourse (on the example of English and Uzbek). Россия “Ученый XXI- века”, 2022,66-с.
2. Galasso J. Analyzing English Grammar. An introduction to feature theory. California State University, Northridge, 2002, 31-page.
3. Maulana H. An analysis of function word and lexical word in magazine (A Case Study in Technology Review Magazine at Rubric “The Tabular View” on May 1954 Edition), 2015, 4-11 pages.
4. Nordquist R. Definition and examples of function words in English. July 2024 (<https://www.thoughtco.com/function-word-grammar-1690876>), 1-2 pages.
5. Ozturk M. Function words in word frequency lists for EFL learners. Bursa-Turkey, 2016, 2-3 pages.
6. Pennebaker J.W, Chung C.K. The psychological functions of function words. Social Communication, January 2007, (<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237378690>), 347-page.